

Rice Grain Dehydration Enhanced by Sheath Plasma*

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Humidity in crops is a key factor considered for the food quality preservation. Various drying processes are implemented as an unavoidable post-harvest process. In this work, we would like to introduce the use of low pressure plasma to electrostatically dry the crop samples, i.e. raw rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) grains. We conducted several preliminary tests in order to compare the average weight loss of the humid raw rice grains, which underwent the 200W microwave and plasma heatings separately. Based on the preliminary results, we found that the microwave drying was still faster the plasma drying by around 51%. However, we suggest that the use of plasma drying leads to the cost effectiveness and the dried crops with the longer lifetime. This is because during plasma drying, sterilization by plasma implementation is ongoing. No extra process and no chemical preservative is required.

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1 Introduction

In agriculture, crops need to be kept at the appropriate humidity for the preservation and the microorganism decrement. This is a significant post-harvest process which are not only implemented to crops for food but also for further breeding. The simplest and cheapest drying is achieved by high temperature evaporation via e.g. sun-drying, hot-air drying, etc. Although, under such evaporation, the crop qualities, such as texture, taste, colour, more or less remain acceptable, high temperature leads to the destruction of vitamins and nutrients in the crops. In addition, the crops may have chances to be in contact with microorganism and insects, e.g. sun-drying outside a building. Drying can be achieved by the use of microwave [1]. The high frequency EM wave directly heats water up rapidly, then the fast and strong evaporation is triggered. However, the surfaces on crops may be opened up leading to the worse texture.

In this work, we would like to introduce a drying technique done by low pressure plasma implementation. Plasma is one of the known states of matter, i.e. gas-like fluid full of free charges. Whenever, a plasma is in contact with a surface, the plasma ions can bombard on the surface. Our assumption is that the bombardment of plasma ions, which are accelerated by the *sheath* electric field, lead to the water vaporization from a humid surface. The preliminary studies on this assumption have been conducted, where the weight loss by vaporization through microwave heating was compared with that of plasma heating as reported in the following sections.

2 Methodology

Our crop samples for drying were raw rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) grains with high humidity. In order to achieve high humidity, the pre-experimental dry grains were soaked in water for 18 hours. After that, the water was drained and then the humid grains were stored in a container with a plastic wrap in a room condition. Each test sample contained the 17.5 g of humid rice.

Our drying system consisted of a borosilicate glass container with an acrylic lid and a sealing gasket. A plastic mesh tray was used to place the rice samples in the container. The working gas was air. A two-stage rotary vacuum pump was used to maintain low pressure. The electrical power for plasma break-down was set up to be approximately 200 W. Drying was performed through the use of microwave heating and plasma heating separately. For the microwave drying, we maintained the pressure in the container as low as 40 mmHg. We used the microwave oven, i.e. Toshiba ER-JD7C(W), as our 200W

heating source. With regards to the plasma heating, a set of hollow electrodes, placed inside the container, connected with the 50Hz AC step-up transformer to generate an air plasma, which are 20 mmHg in pressure and 200 W in power approximately.

3 Result and Discussion

We conducted a set of the preliminary results. Figures 1a and 1b represent the pre-experimental dry and humid rice grains. Figures 1c and 1d represent the post experimental dried rice grains by the 10-minute use of plasma and microwave heatings.

Fig. 1: a. pre-experimental dry and b. humid rice grains, and dried rice grains by c. plasma and d. microwave heatings.

As can be seen from figures 1a-1d, the color of both dried samples are no difference from the pre-experimental dry sample. The humidity in the samples was decreased observed by the weight loss and the colour of the samples. We have recorded the difference between the initial and final weights of the samples. From the repetitive tests, the average weight loss of the samples dried by microwave was 2.2 g, while that dried by plasma was 1.3 g. The percentage of difference by the uses of these two mechanisms was around 51%. The final temperature of the selected samples from both heating mechanisms were about the same, i.e. 38°C. From this, drying by microwave is undoubtedly faster than that by plasma.

We comment that the plasma drying is enhanced by an electrostatic force. The origin of the force is due to the sheath electric field generated by the negatively floating potential setting up by equilibrium charges deposited on the surface [2]. The force mainly accelerates plasma ions to be at least Bohm speed to bombard and transfer momentum onto the humid surface. Water molecules should be released by direct ion bombardment on them and also by indirect water vaporization during temperature rising under low pressure, which is also caused by ion bombardment on the structure of samples. In addition, the rice sample dried by plasma sheath has no contamination, physically observed by eyes, for a long time. This is in contrast to the rest samples. This implies that charged species and electromagnetic wave during air plasma discharge should provide sterilization.

Further studies in detail on the mechanism behind the plasma drying and investigation on the crop qualities, e.g. texture, taste, odor, etc., will be reported elsewhere.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the preliminary results suggest that the microwave drying is still faster than plasma drying. However, plasma drying may lead to other advantages, e.g. food preservation without chemical preservative, sterilization by plasma, cost-effective due to the fact that drying and sterilization are conducted simultaneously. In addition, the sample temperature after exposing to plasma is not high, so we anticipate that most nutrients are preserved. The further studies on this issue need to be carried on.

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